

Identification of Candida Species from Different Respiratory Samples by Using the Phenotypic Method in a Tertiary Care Centre

Anju Mahor¹, T. Thilagawathi², Shashi Gandhi³, Suneel Kumar Ahirwar⁴

¹Assistant professor, Department of Microbiology, Mahatma Gandhi Memorial Medical College, Indore, Madhya Pradesh

²PG Resident, Department of Microbiology, Mahatma Gandhi Memorial Medical College, Indore, Madhya Pradesh

³Professor, Department of Microbiology, Mahatma Gandhi Memorial Medical College, Indore, Madhya Pradesh

⁴Associate Professor, Department of Microbiology, Mahatma Gandhi Memorial Medical College, Indore, Madhya Pradesh

Received: 25-10-2023 / Revised: 23-11-2023 / Accepted: 26-12-2023

Corresponding Author: Dr. Suneel Kumar Ahirwar

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background and Objective: In recent years, the incidence of Candidiasis has witnessed a concerning upsurge, resulting in a significant healthcare challenge. These infections are further enhanced by factors like the widespread use of broad-spectrum antimicrobials, chemotherapy-induced neutropenia, and the presence of medical devices. One factor that may be crucial in limiting disseminated candidiasis is the colonisation of Candida species in the respiratory systems of susceptible hosts. This study was designed to identify Candida species in all respiratory samples.

Material Method: Sampling was conducted from 2021 to 2023. A total of 86 clinical isolates of Candida species were obtained from the respiratory samples of both immunocompromised and immunocompetent patients. The samples were initially inoculated on SDA and examined under a KOH mount. The growth was identified using conventional microbiological techniques.

Result: In our study, *Candida albicans* (n=45 / %=54.65) was most isolated, followed by *Candida tropicalis* (n=26 / %=32.55) and then *Candida krusei* (n=5 / %=8.13), *Candida dublinensis* (n=1 / %=2.32), and *Candida glabrata* (n=1 / %=2.32). In our study, 30–50 years is the most common affected age group.

Conclusion: In recent decades, non-*Albicans* candida has become more widely reported. Early and accurate diagnosis is very essential for the successful management of patients.

Keywords: *Candida* species, SDA, respiratory infection.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Candida species are a part of the normal skin, mucous membrane, and gastrointestinal tract flora. They are often isolated from respiratory secretions in patients on mechanical ventilation because of aspiration of previously colonised oropharyngeal or stomach contents, or seeding of the lungs during hematogenous spread [1].

Significant mortality and morbidity have resulted from the alarmingly high prevalence of *Candida* infections in recent times. A number of *Candida* species are known to cause fungal infections in humans, including *Candida albicans* and non-*albicans* *Candida* spp. like *C. tropicalis*, *C. parapsilosis*, *C. glabrata*, *C. krusei*, *C. guilliermondii*, *C. dubliniensis*, and *C. auris* [2]. Among the *Candida* species, *Candida albicans* is usually regarded as the main pathogen. Over the

past few decades, there has been a noticeable rise in the frequency of non-*albicans* species [3, 4]. Both healthy people and those with compromised immunity are at significant danger from these fungal diseases. With the help of medical devices *Candida* invades tissues, subdues immune systems, and frequently results in serious infections [5].

Candida grows and invades due to a number of factors, including lower phagocytic activity, chemotherapy-induced neutropenia, parenteral feeding, and broad-spectrum antibiotics [6]. Phenotypic methods are used to routinely identify yeast species isolated from clinical samples. They consist of two parts: microscopic observation of fungal structures in the clinical samples and culture, and macroscopic observation of colony shape, size, and colour on an agar plate. These

methods are still regarded as the gold standard for identification. In order to identify the infecting species, clinical culture is typically followed by biochemical analysis based on chromogenic medium [7]. Regardless of the diagnostic technique employed, it is essential to early identification of *Candida* species causing an infection in order to promptly determine the best course of treatment, lower mortality, contain outbreaks, and conduct epidemiological research [8]

Material Method: This was a retrospective laboratory-based study conducted over a period of three years (January 2021 to December 2023) in the department of Microbiology at Mahatma Gandhi Memorial Medical College, Indore.

All the respiratory samples, like sputum, bronchial alveolar lavage (BAL), endotracheal secretions, and pleural fluid that were received in the mycology laboratory were included in this study. BAL, pleural fluid, and endotracheal secretions

were concentrated by centrifugation at 1500–2000 g for 10 minutes. Sputum samples were treated with N-acetyl cysteine prior to inoculation on Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA). All samples were first observed under a KOH mount (10%) and then inoculated on 2 sets of plain SDA and SDA with cycloheximide. The tubes were incubated at both 25°C and 37°C. The tubes were observed on alternate days for the first week and then weekly for 4 weeks. Growth was isolated and identified using standard microbiological methods. Yeast identification included grams staining, germ tube testing, CHROM agar identification, and cornmeal agar (CMA) identification techniques.

Result

A total of 619 respiratory samples were evaluated in this study. Out of 619 respiratory samples, sputum 487 (79%) was the most common, followed by BAL 123 (20%) and pleural fluid 9 (1%). (Fig1)

Figure 1:

Figure 2:

Out of 619, 86 (13.9%) were culture-positive for *Candida* spp. The most common age group affected was 30 to 50 years old. Males were more commonly affected than females.

Isolation rates from sputum were highest (69 samples; 80.2%), followed by BAL (15 samples; 17.4%) and pleural fluid (2 samples; 2.3%). A total of 7 samples were both KOH and culture-positive, but the rest of the samples were positive only by the culture method. In sputum samples, *Candida albicans* (37 isolates; 43.02%) was most isolated, followed by *Candida tropicalis* (20 isolates; 23.25%), and then *Candida krusei* (5 isolates;

5.81%), *Candida dublinensis* (2 isolates; 2.32%), and *Candida glabrata* (2 isolates; 2.32%). In BAL fluid samples, *Candida albicans* (10 isolates; 11.62%) was most isolated, followed by *Candida tropicalis* (7 isolates; 8.12%). In pleural fluid samples, one *Candida tropicalis* and two *Candida krusei* were isolated.

Overall, in respiratory samples, *Candida albicans* (45 isolates; 54.65%) was the most isolated, followed by *Candida tropicalis* (26 isolates; 32.55%), and then *Candida krusei* (5 isolates; 8.13%), *Candida dublinensis* (1 isolate; 2.32%), and *Candida glabrata* (1 isolate; 2.32%).

Figure 3:

Figure 4: Figure showing Budding yeast cells and pseudohyphae in koh mount

Figure 5: showing growth of *Candida* spp on SDA tubes.

Figure 6: Chrom agar showing different *Candida* species growth

Figure 7: Germ tube test of *Candida albicans*.

Figure 8: Dalmau growth of *Candida krusei*

Figure 9: Dalmau growth of *Candida albicans*.

Discussion

In immunocompetent patients, invasive *Candida* pneumonia is so uncommon that its very existence is disputed. When it happens, it's thought to be caused by either aspirating colonized oropharyngeal or stomach contents, which is less common, or seeding the lungs from hematogenous dispersion. The identification of yeast and inflammatory cells in lung tissue through histologic analysis is necessary for the final diagnosis of pulmonary *Candida* infection.

The diagnosis of *Candida* pneumonia is so challenging because histology is rarely accessible clinically, and less intrusive methods cannot differentiate between colonization and infection [9]. Treating fungal infections in hospitalised and immunocompromised patients is a major issue. Infections caused by *Candida* spp. have significantly grown over the past three decades, particularly by non-*albicans* species. Long-term use of antibiotics, which even-

tually changes the natural flora, corticosteroid use, surgical procedures, malnutrition, and hormonal imbalance all increase an individual's susceptibility to candidiasis in immunocompetent people.

Extended usage of commonly prescribed antifungal medications changes the occurrence of *Candida* spp [2, 10] In this study, out of all respiratory samples, 13.9% were culture-positive for *Candida* spp. and among all respiratory samples, sputum samples (80.2%) showed the highest positivity rate. Similarly, Athira Jayaram et al. showed the highest positivity from sputum samples [11].

In the present study, males were more affected, which is similar to many other studies related to respiratory tract infections [12, 13]. The most common affected age group is 30–50 years old. In this study, *Candida albicans* was the most common isolate from all respiratory samples, which is similar to the result shown by M.Taghizadeh et al. and El-Badrawy et al. [14, 15]. In the current study, *C.*

tropicalis was the most common non-Albican candida reported, which is similar to the results shown in many studies [16, 17, 18]

Conclusion

We have concluded that candida infections in the respiratory tract less commonly occur but remain important causes of morbidity. In recent decades, non-Albicans candida has become more widely reported. Early and accurate diagnosis is very essential for the successful management of patients.

References

- Murray PR, Van Scoy RE, Roberts GD. Should yeasts in respiratory secretions be identified? *Mayo Clin Proc.* 1977; 52:42–45.
- Pradeep Reddy Anam, Ved Prakash, Deepika Verma and Ramesh Babu Myneni, Prevalence of Candida species and their Susceptibility to Triazoles in Clinical Isolates from a Tertiary Care Hospital, *J Pure Appl Microbiol.* 2023; 17(4):2437-2442. doi: 10.22207/ JPAM. 17. 4.41.
- Al., R. A. K. et. Characterisation and antifungal susceptibility testing for candida species in a tertiary care hospital. *J. Heal. Sci. Res.*2, (2011).
- B, V. K., G, A. K., Swapna, M. and Easow, J. M. Isolation and identification of candida species from various clinical samples in a tertiary care hospital. 5, 3520–3522 (2017)
- Athira Jayaram, Khushboo Sareen, Ashiwini Dedwal, Sushma Pednekar, Sunil Bhamare, Swati Mulshingkar, Rajesh Karyakarte, Mycological Profile of Respiratory Tract Samples in a Tertiary Care Hospital from Western India, *International Journal of Health Sciences and Research*, Vol.11; Issue: 8; August 2021.
- Durga Shankar Meena Deepak Kumar, Candida Pneumonia: An Innocent Bystander or a Silent Killer? *Brief Report, Med Princ Pract* 2022;31:98–102.,
- Montes K, Ortiz B, Galindo C, Figueroa I, Braham S, Fontecha G (2019) Identification of Candida species from clinical samples in a Honduran Tertiary Hospital. *Pathogens* 8(4):237. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens8040237>.
- Sanglard, D. Emerging Threats in Antifungal-Resistant Fungal Pathogens. *Front. Med. (Lausanne)* 2016, 3, 11. [CrossRef]
- Meersseman W, Lagrou K, Spriet I et al. Significance of the isolation of Candida species from airway samples in critically ill patients: a prospective, autopsy study. *Intensive Care Med* 2009; 35:1526–31.
- Benjamin J. Moss, and Daniel M. Musher, Candida species in community-acquired pneumonia in patients with chronic aspiration, *Moss and Musher Pneumonia*, (2021) 13:12.
- Athira Jayaram, Khushboo Sareen, Ashiwini Dedwal, Sushma Pednekar, Sunil Bhamare, Swati Mulshingkar, Rajesh Karyakarte, Mycological Profile of Respiratory Tract Samples in a Tertiary Care Hospital from Western India, *International Journal of Health Sciences and Research*, Vol.11; Issue: 8; August 2021.
- Oveimar De La Cruz, MDa, Fernanda P. Silveira, MD, MS, Respiratory Fungal Infections in Solid Organ and Hematopoietic Stem Cell Transplantation, *Clin Chest Med* 38 (2017) 727–739.
- Mona M. Ahmeda, Ayman A. Farghalyb, Riham H. Raafata, Waleed M. Abd Elsattar, Study of the prevalence and pattern of fungal pneumonias in respiratory intensive care units, *Egyptian Journal of Bronchology*, Vol. 13 No. 4, October-December 2019.
- Mojtaba Taghizadeh Armaki1(Ph.D student), Mohammad Taghi Hedayati2*(Ph.D), Saeed Mahdavi Omran3(Ph.D), Sasan Saber4(MD), Mahdi Abastabar2(Ph.D), Akbar Hosseinnjad1(MSc Student), Identification and Antifungal Susceptibility Testing of Candida species isolated from Bronchoalveolar Lavage samples, *International Journal of Molecular and Clinical Microbiology*, y 1 (2014) 358-364.
- Mohammad Khairy El-Badrawy, Amany Ragab Elsaied, Asmaa Adel Metwally Ibrahim, Ahmed Elsayed Eladl and Rehab Ahmad Elmorsey, Prevalence and pattern of isolated fungi from bronchoalveolar lavage among patients with lung cancer: a prospective cross-sectional study, *The Egyptian Journal of Bronchology*, (2023)17:7
- Golia S, Reddy KM, Karjigi KS, Hittinahalli V. Speciation of Candida using chromogenic and cornmeal agar with determination of fluconazole sensitivity. *Al Ameen J Med Sci.* 2013; 6(2):163-6.
- Vijaya D, Harsha TR, Nagaratanamma T. Candida speciation using CHROM agar. *J Clin Diagn Res.* 2011; 5(4):755-7.
- Adhikari R, Joshi S. Species distribution and anti-fungal susceptibility of candidemia at a multi super-speciality center in Southern India. *Ind J Med Microbiol.* 2013; 29:309-11.